

Prevalence of Preventive Measures of COVID-19 and its Associated Factors Among People Attending Health Facility, in Arada Sub-City, Addis Ababa, Ethiopia, 2022.

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Abstract

Statement of the problem: corona virus is highly contagious disease and has challenging impact in health care system, social, economic, and psychological wellbeing of humanity. The world health organization (WHO) declares corona virus as a public health emergency of international concern on 30 January, 2020.the best prevention is to avoid being exposed to the virus.

OBEJECTIVE: The objective of the study is to assess the prevalence of preventive measures and associated factors towards coronary virus (Covid19) among community attending to health center in arada sub-city, Addis Ababa, Ethiopia from April -August/2022G.C.

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METHODS and Materials: this thesis applied institutional based cross-sectional study. Systematic random sampling method was used to select study participants. Structured and pre tested questionnaire were used for data collection. The data was then analyzed by SPSS version 25 statistical package software. Descriptive statics using frequency, proportion and table were used to present the study result. Binary logistic regression analyze was employed to see association between practice of preventive measures and different risk factors. Variables showing significant association in bivariate analyses were fitted to multivariate regression model to identify the independent contribution of each variable for practice of preventive measures.

Result: the magnitude of practice of preventive measure of COVID 19 in this study was 32.7.factors associated with the practice among educated people were(AOR:1.98;95%CI:1.15,3.45).Family members of more than five were (AOR:1.68;95%CI:1.04,2.06), Family income (AOR:3.84;95%CI:0.13,0.54).Those who were married (AOR:2.34;95%CI:1.32,4.42).Knowledge assessment were (AOR:3.31;95%CI:1.66,6.66),and Attitude assessment were (AOR:1.98;95%CI:0.13,0.54).The finding showed statically significant association with practice of preventive measures with P-value less than 0.05.

Conclusion: the magnitude of practice of preventive measures was low compared to previous studies. The study recommends to implement preventive measures with available set up, to give continuous information about the danger of Covid19.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. BACKGROUND

Coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) is an emerging respiratory infection and is known to cause illness ranging from the common cold to severe acute respiratory syndrome. COVID-19 is known to spread from human-to-human through droplets and direct contact. In December 2019, a novel corona virus (COVID-19) was detected in three patients with pneumonia connected to the cluster of acute respiratory illness cases from Wuhan, China [1]. The pathogen of this disease was confirmed as a novel corona virus by molecular methods and was initially named as 2019 novel corona virus (2019-nCoV); however, on January 30, 2020, the WHO declared the COVID-19 outbreak as the sixth public health emergency of international concern. Therefore, this outbreak constitutes a public health risk through the international spread of disease and requires a coordinated international response. Increased dissemination of information through use of the internet is associated with increased

transmission of information from all geographical regions and across disciplines regarding recognition of COVID-19 [2].

Corona viruses are single-stranded RNA, non-segmented, enveloped viruses that cause illness ranging in severity from the common cold to severe and fatal illness [3]. Robust estimates for final case fatality risk for COVID-19 are still lacking and biased due to incomplete outcome data [4]. To date, there are no vaccines that protect COVID-19. The best way to prevent infection is avoiding exposure to this virus [5]. Knowledge and implementation of the community on the measures recommended by Communicable Disease Control (CDC) and World Health Organization (WHO) for both prevention and case finding are crucial [6].

The most commonly reported clinical symptom in laboratory-confirmed cases were fever (88%), followed by dry cough (68%), fatigue (38%), sputum production (33%), dyspnea (19%), sore throat (14%), headache (14%) and myalgia or arthralgia (15%) [7]. Less common symptoms were diarrhea (4%) and vomiting (5%) [8]. About 80% of reported cases in China had mild to moderate disease, 13.8% had severe disease and 6.1% were critical [9]. Current estimates suggest a median incubation period from five to six days for COVID-19, with a range from one to up to 14 days [10].

As of December 2019, until August 27, 2020, 23:42 GMT, a total of 24,603,578 confirmed cases, including 61,536 with severe illness, 17,072,656 recovery and 834,719 deaths had been reported worldwide. In Ethiopia, there were 46,407 confirmed cases, including 330 with severe illness, 16,829 recovery and 745 deaths reported since March 13 to August 27, 2020, 23:42 GMT. To date (August 27/2020), COVID-19 has affected people in more than 215 countries, including Ethiopia, and has become a global threat. America has the largest number of patients with COVID-19 (6,044,411), followed by Brazil (3,764,493) and India (3,384,575). Ethiopia was 52 ranking countries on the world level. However, asymptomatic patients or patients with mild COVID-19 symptoms may not seek health care, nor receive diagnosis, which leads to underestimation of the burden of COVID-19. African countries with the highest estimated numbers of COVID-19 cases were South Africa, Egypt, Morocco, Nigeria and Ethiopia [11]. 54.3% of those infected with SARS-CoV-2 were male with a median age of 56 years. Patients who required intensive care support were older and had multiple comorbidities such as cardiovascular, cerebrovascular, endocrine, digestive, and respiratory disease. Those in intensive care were also more likely to report dyspnea, dizziness, abdominal pain, and anorexia [12].

The impact of the COVID-19 outbreak on the East and Horn of Africa is expected to be far-reaching and more catastrophic than for high income countries, these pre-existing conditions such as the

population size, status of health systems and health workforce are expected to worsen any health impacts from COVID-19 [13, 14].

Ethiopia is the second most populous nation in Africa, and home to close to 9% of the African population. Ethiopia responds to COVID-19 started early. On January, the government introduced passenger-screening protocols at Addis Ababa's international airport, and further preparation continued in January and February. The first report of a COVID-19 case in Ethiopia was on March 13, two days after the global pandemic was declared. National responses were scaled up soon after, and a state of emergency was declared on April 8 [15]. In response to COVID-19, the federal and regional governments in Ethiopia have been taking a series of policy actions. These include closing schools, restricting use of public transportation, banning large meetings, and suspending sporting and religious gatherings [16].

The following basic measures to reduce transmission of COVID-19 have been recommended by the WHO and have been adopted by the Ethiopian Government, such as wash hands frequently using soap, maintain social distancing, stay informed and follow advice given by healthcare provider, stay at home. If you begin to feel sick and if you develop fever or cough or experience difficulty breathing, seek medical advice and call in advance the center. Even though COVID-19 case diagnosis and knowledge on prevention remain vital components of the control strategies, little is known about the knowledge, risk perception and perceived self-efficacy of the community in the context of Ethiopia. The Ethiopian government is expanding its diagnosis system in order to increase accessibility of COVID-19 diagnosis and treatment to regional and zonal levels. Evidence on this subject would contribute to the prevention, control of COVID-19 as well as on the management of its impact. Therefore, this study aimed to assess the prevalence of preventive measures of Covid19 and associated factors among people attending health facilities.

1.2. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) reported in late December 2019 from Wuhan, China is one of the shocking pandemics for humans. [20 ,21] WHO affirmed COVID-19 as a pandemic on 11 March 2020.[22] The pandemic is challenging both for developed and developing nation's healthcare system, social, economic, and psychological wellbeing of humanity.

Globally, As of 20 January 2021, more than 97 million and 2 million peoples are infected and died, respectively. [23] WHO reported more than 2.1 million confirmed cases of COVID-19, including 142,229 deaths in 213 countries, areas or territories [24]

In Europe the crisis of Covid19 was introduced in January 2020 during January 2020 to July 2020 the highest number of cases were recorded in April (850,681) Eastern Europe has been the most severely hit region with 9,856,455 cases and 209,230 deaths, followed by 8,369,494 cases and 193,963 deaths in western Europe. The second highest number of deaths was reported in southern Europe (197,457).[25]

The six countries also account for 65.62% of Covid19 related death in Europe: Russia (77,068, 10.45%), UK (112,798, 15.29%), France (78,956, 10.7%), Spain (62,295, 8.44%), Italy (91,273, 12.7%) and Germany (61,675, 8.36%). The overall case fatality rate (CFR) of European regions was 2.35% varying from 2.12% in Eastern Europe to 2.54% in Northern and southern Europe. [25]

The economy of European countries reported shortages of health resource. The economies tried to streamline the resources by diverting fund towards the building up health resource and infrastructure. Videos and telephone consulting were scaled-up. Numerous digital tools such as mobile app and web platform were employed for remote health monitoring, consultation and contact tracing.[25]

while Africa was among the last regions the virus touched with the First case of covid 19 reported in Egypt on February 14, 2020. In Africa, more than 3.3 million cases were reported with a rising death toll of over 81 thousand people. The most-affected countries so far are South Africa (confirmed cases = 2783, mortality = 1.8%), Egypt (confirmed cases = 2844, mortality = 7.2%), Morocco (confirmed cases = 2564, mortality = 5.3%), Algeria (confirmed cases = 2418, mortality = 15.0%) and Cameroon (confirmed cases = 1016, mortality = 2.1%)

However, due to inadequate testing capacity for COVID-19 the true number of cases may remain undetected, which makes it challenging to predict or conclude the true epidemiology of COVID-19 in the continent.[26]

Indeed, the economy is simultaneously affected by a supply and a demand shock. On the supply side, the lockdown leads to a decrease in production as capital is largely unused and workers are at home while on the demand side there is a decrease in demand as the rest of the world are reducing their consumption. The combined effect is a reduction by 10.3% in gross domestic product (GDP) in the mild scenario and 14.14% in the severe scenario. The reduction in total production leads to a fall of total labor demand from the industries. However, for both scenarios, the increase in the unemployment rate is greater.[38]

The limited testing capacity, shortage of trained staff required for diagnostics and intensive care units (ICU), inadequate ventilators and ICU facilities (needed in severe cases of COVID-19), lack of

personal protective equipment (PPE) for healthcare workers and scarcity of funds for the health sector, are some of the continent's core healthcare related issues, which make it more susceptible to the COVID-19 pandemic [27–30]

strategic measures, which include complete lockdowns, travel bans, closing of schools, companies, and offices, ban on large gatherings (including religious, sports, social and other events), systematic quarantines, increased testing capacity and strict infection control measures, are being implemented throughout the African continent to control the spread of COVID-19. [31].

Ethiopia is the 5th high case reporting country in Africa. In Ethiopia 109,534 cases are detected, among which 1700 have died and 69,315 have recovered. [33]

According to world Bank House hold survey 23 percent of household had ran out of food in the previous 30 days; in 21 percent of household, an adult went hungry but did not eat; and in 14 percent an adult went a whole day without eating.

In young live survey ,17 percent of household (18 percent urban and 16 percent rural) reported that they ran out of food at least once since the covid 19 outbreak began in Ethiopia (young lives 2020). in the SPIR survey covering PSNP woredas in Amhara and Oromia, indicated that 50 percent of household in Oromia and 12 percent of the household in Amhara were severely food insecure in the past 30 days. The IFPRI survey in Addis Ababa was specifically designed to assess change in food security and June identified that 6 percent of the sampled household were severely food insecure.

In addition, to this This survey find that 27 percent of the respondents reported that at least one member of their household had lost their jobs because of the pandemic (young lives 2020). the OPM survey with poor and vulnerable urban households find that more than 60 percent of household reported to have reduced their working hours since the onset of the pandemic.

The world bank household survey reported, in April ,61 percent of urban household and 52 percent of rural household reported income loss since the pandemic began.

In Addis Ababa survey conducted by IFPRI IN early may, 58 percent of respondents said that the income in the past month were lower or much lower than usual In June this number had increase to 67 percent.

The government of Ethiopia initially takes basic measures such as obligatory quarantine periods for passengers, gathering restrictions, closures of school and religious places, reducing the number of passengers in public transports, and mandatory wearing of face masks in public places. (35) Also,

COVID-19 preventive measures are disseminated through media, cell-phone, and COVID-19 reported daily by the Minister of Health.[36]

Moreover, a state of emergency was declared on April 8, 2020, to stop the spread of COVID-19. However, on the ground, all the suggested preventive and control measures are not viably actualized. On the other hand, information about the disease and its preventive measures were not extensively disseminated to the rural communities.[34] Confusing the symptoms of COVID-19 with a common cold could challenge the practice of early treatment-seeking when COVID-19 is accompanied with flu/ common cold-like symptoms. Moreover, confusion can intensify bias and social stigma related to COVID-19[37]

1.3 justification of the study

In Ethiopia the positivity rate of Covid19 has increased with time to time. findings, show that living or working in an area such as, bus station, health center, school, public transport, are high risk area and associated with the community knowledge about the pandemic and poor practice to prevent the disease.

There is a huge gap in preventing the pandemic, since its new phenomenon, and the general public has little knowledge to the practice the prevention of the disease. This indicates, the need for, research in every aspect, but in Developing countries prioritizing the prevention is the only ways to curb the pandemic.to do this the community must know and implement preventive mechanisms. For the intervention to be successful there is a need to have evidence that show the level of the practice towards Covid19 preventive strategies at community level. Therefore, this research aimed at assessing the practice and associated factors towards the prevention of Covid19 in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia.

1.3. SIGNIFICANT OF THE STUDY

To the best of our knowledge, the current study in Arada sub-city was examine prevalence of preventive measures of Covid19 and associated factors of Covid19 in Health centers, Addis Ababa. To prevent and control Covid19 outbreak in community, there is an urgent need to understand the community prevention practice and prevention associated factors towards the pandemic at this critical moment. This study investigated gaps in prevention practices and associated factors towards Covid19 among community visiting Health centers. This might further reduce the risk of Covid19 transmission.

This study was also guided several stakeholders and policy makers by identifying specific gap on limitations of prevention practices towards Covid19 in community. Finally, this study was also

servicing as a baseline for future research on Covid19 outbreaks which may provide essential information for researchers and policy makers.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. PREVENTION OF COVID 19

Information on the responses and behaviors of Chinese citizens were collected through a cross-sectional, internet-based survey using Dongxiang Doctor's public account on We Chat. Over half the participants (n=5878, 57.7%) were confident that the epidemic could be curbed in China; 92.4% (n=9427) opened windows for ventilation more frequently than usual; 97.9% (n=9986) used masks in public; 95.7% (n=9759) avoided large crowds and stayed at home as much as possible; and 97.9% (n=9988) washed their hands more often than usual.

As for circumstances under which respondents felt inclined to wash their hands, 88.1% (n=8980) of participants washed their hands after touching public goods, 94.8% (n=9665) after toilet use, 91.5% (n=9331) after returning home, 66.5% (n=6782) after coughing or sneezing, and 87.5% (n=8923) before eating. In terms of how participants washed their hands, 86.7% used soap and running water in most cases. [39]

Another, cross-sectional design was employed using an anonymous online survey administered through Qualtrics Survey Software in District of Columbia, and English-speaking Canada (all 10 provinces except Quebec) was obtained. Almost all respondents agreed with the statement: "I strictly followed my state's preventative measures (e.g., social distancing, wearing a mask) during the COVID-19 outbreak. [40]

community-based cross-sectional study design was employed to identify predictors of adherence to COVID 19 prevention measures among North Shoa zone, Amhara regional state, Ethiopia. The overall adherence level of the community towards the recommended safety measures of COVID-19 was 44.1% (95% CI = 41.1, 48.2). Only nine percent of participants did not practice hand washing with soap and 42.2% of the respondents did not utilize sanitizers to clean hand. [41]

Additionally, Health institution based cross sectional study was conducted Among Northeast Ethiopia the total participants 81 (15.8%) were having history of touching others for greeting. Moreover, nearly half of them, 266 (51.9%), did not have the practice of washing their hands with soap after touching anything or anyone. [42] A cross-sectional in person survey within high-risk group In Addis Ababa. The preventive measures towards COVID-19 were found to be low (49%, 95% CI: 48–50). [43]

2.2. ASSOCIATED FACTORS TOWARDS PREVENTION OF COVID 19

The study done among 6910 participants in China showed that knowledge was significantly different across genders, age-groups, categories of marital status, education levels, and residence.^[44] Multiple linear regression analysis showed that male gender, age-group of 16-29 years (vs. 30-49 years), marital status of never-married (vs. married), education of bachelor's degree or lower (vs. master degree and above), and occupations of unemployment and students (vs. mental labor) were significantly associated with lower knowledge score.^[44]

A cross-sectional online survey was administered in May 2020 to members of a paid panel representative of the Canadian population by age, gender, official language, and religion. More than 90% of respondents reported confidence in the ability to comply with a variety of public health measures. However, only 51% reported preparedness for illness in terms of expectation to work if sick or access to paid sick days. Risk perceptions, attitudes, and behaviors varied by demographic variables. Men, younger age groups, and those in the paid workforce were less likely to consider public health measures to be effective, and had less confidence in their ability to comply.^[45]

Nearly, half of participants (47.1%) had inadequate knowledge of COVID-19. The odds of adherence to safety measures of COVID-19 were 1.60 times higher among communities who perceived that they were not susceptible to COVID-19 than their counterparts. Members of the community who did not have a perception of barriers of COVID-19 measures was 3.36 times higher on poor adherence of COVID-19 recommended preventive measures as compared to those who had a perception of barriers of COVID-19 measures.^[41]

About 4.9% (25/513) study participants had low level of knowledge about the transmission, prevention and control of COVID-19 pandemic. Majority of study participants who had low level of knowledge about the pandemic were living with a family size greater than 6. Female study participants had 32 times odds of having low level of knowledge in comparison with their male counterparts.^[42]

The proportion of study participants who had low level of practice towards the prevention and control of COVID-19 pandemic was 14.62% (75/513). Study participants who had 1–3 family members had more than five times the likelihood of having low practice level towards the control and prevention of the pandemic in comparison with study participants who had greater than 6 family members. Study participants in the age category between 16 and 65 years were 35 times more likely to have poor practice compared to those study participants who were older than 65 years. Low level knowledge and cigarette smoking habit showed a positive (exposing) statistically significant association with poor level of practice whereas gender of study participants did not show any significant association.

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In another way study participants who had travel history and those who had usual alcohol drinking habit had an inverse statistical association with low level practice towards the prevention and control means of COVID-19 in reference to their counterparts.[42]

In Ethiopia, the study found that occupation, religion, income, and knowledge on the transmission and prevention of COVID-19 were found to be associated with the practice of precautionary measures against COVID-19.

The odds of being knowledgeable on the transmission mechanisms of COVID-19 among male participants were 0.87 times less likely than females. As age increases, the likelihood of being knowledgeable about the transmission modes of COVID-19 increases. Age group older than 64 years were 14 times. More likely to be knowledgeable on the transmission of COVID-19 than those who were younger than 18 years old. Regarding the occupation of respondents, health workers and grocery store workers were 2.25 and 2.22 times, respectively, more likely to be knowledgeable on the transmission mode of COVID-19 than other occupations. As income increases, the likelihood of being knowledgeable about the methods of transmission of COVID-19 also increases; however, above some level of income this is no longer the case. Participants whose income was greater than 10,000 Ethiopian Birr were 49% less likely to be knowledgeable about the transmission mechanism of COVID-19 than low-income participants (<1000 ETB).[43]

Regarding religion, Muslims participants were at 0.42 lower odds of implementing the precautionary measures of COVID-19 than others. The implementation of precautionary measures against COVID-19 was found to be lower among higher income groups. Those who earned more than 10,000 ETB per month had 0.42 lower odds of practicing the precautionary measures against COVID-19 than those with lower income.[43]

Participants who had good knowledge on mode of transmission and prevention mechanisms of COVID-19 were four times and fifteen times more likely, respectively, to implement the precautionary measures of COVID-19. [43]

3. OBEJECTIVE

3.1. General objective

To assess the prevalence of preventive measures and associated factors towards coronary virus (Covid19) among community attending to health center in Arada sub-city, Addis Ababa, Ethiopia from April -August /2022G.C.

3.2. Specific objective

To Examine Prevalence of preventive measures towards Covid19 among community attending health center in Arada sub-city

To investigate associated factors for preventive measures towards Covid19 among community attending health center in Arada sub-city.

4. METHDOLGY

4.1. study area and period

The study was conducted in Arada sub city, Addis Ababa the capital city of Ethiopia from May 15-August 20/2022 G.C. The district is located in the northern area of the city, nearby the center. The total area of the sub city is 9.91-kilometer cube and 225,999 people live in the area. Out of them 105,963 were Male and 12,036 were female. . The sub city has six general hospitals and Eleven health centers and above 60 private clinics. The sub city has Seven governmental secondary schools, and twenty-two primary school.

Figure one: Map of sub-city in Addis Ababa.

4.2. Study design

Institutional based cross sectional study design will be used.

4.2.1. Source population

All people who visit Health center in Arada sub-city, Addis Ababa

4.2.2. Study population

All randomly selected individual who visit health center in Arada sub-city during the study period.

4.3. Inclusion and Exclusion criteria

4.3.1. Inclusion criteria

All individual visits the health center

Individual above the age of 18 year

4.3.2. Exclusion criteria

Those individuals who aren't able to communicate due to mental or sever illness

4.5. Sample Size

The sample size is calculated by using single proportion formula formula ($n = (Z \alpha/2)^2 p (1-p) / d^2$), by considering the study conducted in Ethiopia on knowledge, practices and associated factors towards the prevention of Covid19 among high-risk group: a cross-sectional study in Addis Ababa Ethiopia using the practice part and considering the following assumptions:

$$\frac{z^2 \alpha / 2 \times p (1 - P)}{d^2}$$

Where, ni= minimum sample size required for the study

Z= standard normal distribution ($z= 1.96$), confidence interval (CI) 95%

P= prevalence of study=49%

d= tolerable margin of error 5% (0.05)

N_f =final sample size

Non respondent rate =5% NRR

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$$\text{Population proportion } n = \frac{(1.96)^2 * 0.49 (1-0.49)}{(0.05)^2} = 383$$

$$n=383$$

Adding 5 % non-respondent rate, the total number of sample size was estimated to be = 371

The total number of people attending health service at selected health center was 2489 which is less than 10,000. Then correction formula was used for sample size determination. $n_f =$;

Where n_f = final sample size

n_0 =initial sample size

N =total sample size

$$n_f = 333$$

4.6. sampling techniques and procedures

From total of 11 health centers in Arada sub-city; four was selected by simple random sampling method. Systematic random sampling was carried out in the selected Health center by proportional allocation of systemic random sampling technique.

$$n_i = n * \frac{N_i}{N}, i= 1,2,3, \dots$$

Where n represents sample size, N_i represents population size of the i^{th} strata and N represents the population size. The people were taking for interview, based on their lists. The interval of the respondents for the interview was determined by dividing the total number of people attending outpatient service in selected health centers to total number of sample of people selected.

$K = \frac{N}{n} = 8$ Where K , is the sampling interval.

Table 1: distribution of sample of people attending health centers by systemic sampling

Health centers	Total number of peoples (Ni)	Proportionally allocated for each ($n_i = n \cdot \frac{N_i}{N}$)
Afenchober woreda 04	805	108
Arada woreda 10	833	111
Semen Mazegaja woreda 04	818	109
Semegn kebed woreda 03	33	4
Total	2489	333

4.7. Study variables

The dependent variables:

Practice of preventive measures

The independent variables:

Socio-demographic

Knowledge about Covid19

Attitudes about Covid19

4.8. OPERATIONAL DEFINITION

Face mask usage: properly covering mouth and nose using Recommended face mask at any time when the participant leaves their home.

Regular hand washing: the process of mechanically removing soil, debris and transient flora from hands using soap and clean water for at least 20-40 seconds after contact with people, touching material and equipment, and surrounding.

Social distancing: the practice of maintaining a greater than usual physical distance (such as, six feet or about 2 meter) from other people or avoiding direct contact with people or object during the in public place outbreak of a contagious distance in order to minimize the exposure or reduce the transmission of infection.

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Attitude Level: Respondents who was correctly answered mean score of the attitude questions was considered as respondent with a positive attitude while the respondents who was correctly answered below the mean score of the attitude was considered as the respondents with negative attitude.

Knowledge level: Respondents who was correctly answer more than the mean score of 9.75 the knowledge question was consider as respondents with a good knowledge level while respondents who was answer under the mean score of the knowledge question was considers as having poor knowledge.

Practice level: the act of actual application of covid 19 preventive measures to reduce the risk factor and enhance protective factors to improve well-being of individuals, families and communities.

4.9. DATA COLLECTION TOOL AND PROCEDURE

Structured questionnaire adapted from different literature was utilized. The questioner consists of socio-demographic part, Knowledge questions, Attitude question, COVID 19 preventive practice questions and covid 19 source of information. These questions were answered on a YES or NO basis with an additional “I don’t know” optional YES/true answer will be assigned 1 point and False/I don’t know/ NO answer will be assigned 0 point. Twelve items was used to assess the knowledge about COVID 19, the item assess the knowledge regarding Etiology, route of transmission, susceptibility, clinical manifestations, All response was summed up and it has a possible value of 0 to 13 to classify the respondents as having good and poor knowledge, the mean knowledge score was computed and participants having greater than or equal to mean knowledge score was considered as having good knowledge.

Similarly, eight items were used to assess the attitude of the respondents. The item was having rating response and for each item, 2 point was given if the response is positive, 1 for a neutral response, and 0 for negative responses. Based on that, the participant may have a possible value from 0 to 16. A participant who was score greater than or equals to the mean was considered as having positive attitude. Practice was measured by six items participant response was scored by giving 1 for possible response “often or more “and 0 for “rarely or less” similarly 1 was given for questions requiring proactive measures to be taken and 0 for responses like “I don’t know what to do”. If participants have score greater or equal to the mean score it is considered as having good practice.

The questionnaire was prepared in English language and translate into Amharic version and then back to English version. Six health professional was assigned to collect the data from the questioner. Timely supervision was under taken by the principal investigator during the data collection period.

4.10. DATA PROCESSING, ANALYSIS AND PRESENTATION

After data collection is over, the data was categorized, coded, and checked for consistency, completeness, then entered, cleaned and analyzed using SPSS version # 25 software. Descriptive statics was carried out to see frequency, mean, median, standard deviation and percentage; data was presented by using Tables, chart and bar graph. Binary logistic regression was used to assess the association between dependent and independent variables. Thus, independent variables with a P-value of < 0.05 were considered as statically significant. Then multivariate logistic regression was used to control potential confounders and to identify factor associated to COVID 19. The model fitness was checked using Hosmer-Lemeshow model fitness test.

4.11. DATA QUALITY CONTROLE

To maintain data quality, training was given for data collector. A properly designed data collection material was developed. Supervision was carried out on daily bases to check completeness, consistency by the principal investigator to keep the quality of data. Correction was carried out if necessary.

4.12. ETHICAL CONSIDERATION

Ethical clearance was obtained from Addis Ababa Medical College Research office. Letter of cooperation was obtained from the department of public health. This ethical clearance as well as a letter of cooperation was sent for Arada sub city to give consent for data collection. Data collection was started after permission is obtained. Data that was collected from the participant was kept in secured in order to maintain confidentiality. Voluntary participation was ensured.

4.13. DISSEMINATION OF THE RESULT

The result of the study was disseminated to Addis Ababa medical college research office, Arada sub city, and different stakeholders located in the sub city.

5.1. Socio-demographic characteristics of participants

A total of 333 eligible participants, were recruited in this study which making an overall response rate of 95%. Table 1 describes the proportion of socio demographic characteristics of the study population.

Age was distributed in normal pattern with the mean age 1.65 and SD was 1.532 and majority of them were found in age group 31-45. Concerning marital status nearly twenty two percent of study subject were married while seventy three percent respondents were single.

Regarding educational status 172(49.3%) of respondents were collage and above but, 26(7.4%) of study subjects didn't have formal education during the study time. Nearly twenty one percent of study subject has family monthly income of greater than three thousand from those who have family monthly income of less than nine hundred.

Table 2: socio-demographic characteristics of people attending health facilities in Arada sub-city health centers, Addis Ababa, Ethiopia, 2022.

Variables	Category	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Age	17-30	126	31.1
	31-45	198	56.7
	>45	9	2.7
Sex	Male	104	29.8
	Female	229	68.8
Marital status	Married	78	22.3
	Unmarried	255	73.1
Educational status	No formal education	26	7.4
	Grade 1-8	41	11.7
	Grade 9-12	94	26.9
	Collage and above	172	49.3
Occupational status	Government employee	131	37.5
	Private	67	19.2
	Unemployed	73	20.9
	Others	46	13.2
Family members	<5	137	39.3
	>5	195	55.9
Religion	Orthodox	190	54.4
	Muslim	76	21.8
	Protestant	59	16.9
	Other	8	2.3
Income level	<900	157	45.0
	900-3000	103	29.5
	>3000	33	20.9

5.2. Knowledge about covid 19

Regarding knowledge about covid 19 264 (75.6 %) of respondents have good knowledge and 68 (19.5%) of respondents have poor knowledge about covid 19 etiology, route of transmission, susceptibility, clinical manifestation

Table 3: knowledge about covid 19 among people attending health facility in Arada sub-city health centers Addis Ababa, Ethiopia, 2022.

Variables	response	number	Percent
There is COVID-19 IN Ethiopia	YES	322	92.3
	NO	11	3.2
There is source of information regarding COVID- 19	YES	256	73.4
	NO	77	22.1
Someone who have history of COVID-19 should isolate him/her self	YES	243	69.6
	NO	90	25.8
Isolation and treatment of infected person can reduce the spread of the virus	YES	298	85.4
	NO	35	10.0
Individual should avoid going to crowded place	YES	308	88.3
	NO	25	7.3
Using prevention method are important to children and young adults	YES	293	84.0
	NO	39	11.2
The virus spread via respiratory droplet of infected individual	YES	196	56.2
	NO	137	39.3
Asymptomatic infected person can transmit the virus to others	YES	270	77.4
	NO	63	18.1
Can all person with COVID-19 Will develop to severe disease	YES	196	56.2
	NO	137	39.3
Currently there is no effective cure drug for covid 19	YES	235	67.3
	NO	98	28.1
Symptom of stuffy nose and sneezing are less common	YES	258	73.9
	NO	75	21.5
Using mask can help to reduce the spread of disease	YES	329	94.3
	NO	4	1.1
Vaccine are available for prevention of COVID 19	YES	280	80.2
	NO	53	15.2

5.3. Attitude towards covid 19

Regarding attitude about covid 19 258 (73.9%) of respondents have good attitude about covid 19 whereas, 75(95.4%) of respondents have poor attitude towards covid 19.

Table 4: Attitude about covid 19 preventive measures among people attending health facility in Arad sub-city health centers Addis Ababa Ethiopia, 2022.

Variable	Response	Number	Percent
Do you think COVID-19 disease is dangerous?	YES	263	75.4
	NO	70	20.1
Do you think that hand washing can prevent /decrease transmission?	YES	270	77.4
	NO	63	18.1
Do you think that wearing a mask prevent/decrease transmission	YES	307	88.0
	NO	26	7.4
Do you think that using alcohol/sanitizer decrease transmission?	YES	317	90.8
	NO	16	4.6
Do you think stay at home /avoid going to crowded place prevent transmission?	YES	324	92.8
	NO	9	2.6
Do you think that keeping social distance will prevent transmission?	YES	305	87.4
	NO	28.0	8.0
Do you agree that COVID-19 will finally be successfully controlled?	YES	197	56.4
	NO	136	39.0
Do you have confidence that Ethiopia can win the battle against the COVID-19 virus?	YES	137	39.3
	NO	196	56.2

5.4. Practice towards preventive measure of covid 19

Regarding practice for covid 19 preventive measures 114 (32.7%) of respondents have good practice while, 219(62.8%) of respondents have poor practice of preventive measures of covid 19.

The overall prevalence of practice of covid 19 in this study was very low which accounted 32.7 %.

Figure 2: prevalence of practice towards preventive measure of covid 19 among people attending health facility in Arada sub-city health center Addis Ababa, Ethiopia, 2022.

5.5. Source of information

Table 5: showing source of information about COVID 19

Variables		Number	Percent
Health professionals	YES	276	79.1
	NO	57	16.3
Social media	YES	313	89.7
	NO	20	5.7
Religious leaders	YES	150	43.0
	NO	183	52.4
No information	YES	0	0
	NO	333	100

5.6. Factors associated with preventive practice of COVID 19

Variable having p-Value less than 0.25 in the bivariate analysis were entered in to the final model and Variable having p-Value less than 0.05 in the multivariate logistic regression were considered as statistically significant.

After multivariate analysis was conducted, two variables (religion and occupational status) were excluded as they were insignificant. in this study the odds of practice of preventive measures of covid 19 among people whose category was Grade 9-8 was 1.98 times higher as compared with those who no formal education (AOR:1.98;95%CI:1.55,3.45).

Individuals whose family income was found in category of 100-3000, were 4 times more likely than that category found in 900 with practice of Covid 19 preventive measures (AOR:3.85;95%CI:2.17,6.84).

The study indicated that people with family member more than 5 were 1.6 times more likely to practice preventive measures of covid 19 (AOR: 1.68;95%CI:1.04,2.69). The study also showed that participants who had married were 2.4 times more likely to practice preventive measure of COVID 19 compared to those who are unmarried with no association (AOR:2.43;95%CI:1.32,4.42).

regarding Knowledge about Covid 19 individuals who have knowledge about COVID 19 were 3.3 times more likely to practice Covid 19 preventive measures (AOR:3.31;95%CI:1.66,6.66).

The study showed individual having good attitude about Covid 19 were 2 times more likely to practice preventive measures of Covid 19(AOR:1.92.;95%CI:0.13,0.54).

Tabel 6: factor associated with practice of COVID 19 preventive measures among people attending health facility in Arada sub-city, Addis Ababa, Ethiopia 2022.

Variables	Category	No% of practiced	No% of not practiced	COR (95%CI)	AOR (95%CI)
Educational level	No formal education	38(27.5%)	26(46.1%)	0.57(0.43-0.76) *	1(0.12,0.10) **
	Grade 1-8	14(34.1%)	27(65.9%)		1.2(0.01,0.23)
	Grade 9-12	26(27.7%)	68(72.3%)		1.46(0.71,2.97)
	Collage and above	74(49%)	98(57%)		1.98(1.15,3.45)
Family income	900	41(26.1%)	116(73.3%)	0.53(0.39-0.70) *	3.20(1.62,6.14)
	1000-3000	28(28.6%)	70(71.4%)		3.85(2.17,6.84) **
	>3000	45(57.7%)	33(42.3%)		3.40(1.82,6.38)
Family members	>5	76(39.0%)	119(61.0%)	1.68(1.05-2.69) *	1.68(1.04,2.69) **
	<5	38(27.5%)	100(72.5%)		
Religion	Orthodox	80(42.1%)	110(57.9%)	1.32(1.02-1.57) *	1
	Muslim	8(10.5%)	68(59.5%)		6.18(2.8,13.5)
	Protestant	26(46.1%)	33(55.9%)		0.97(0.51,1.66)
	Others	0(0%)			1
Marital status	Married	16(20.5%)	62(79.5%)	0.41(0.23-0.75) *	2.43(1.32,4.42) **
	Unmarried	98(38.4%)	157(61.6%)		1
Occupational status	Government	63(48.1%)	68(51.9%)	1.25(1.03-1.51) *	0.36(0.11,1.17)
	Private	11(16.4%)	56(83.6%)		1.69(0.46,6.24)
	Unemployed	18(24.7%)	55(75.3%)		1.01(0.29,3.55)
	Others	18(39.1%)	28(60.9%)		0.51(0.14,1.86)
Knowledge	Yes	103(39.0%)	161(61.0%)	3.31(1.66-6.67) *	3.31 (1.66,6.6) **
	No	11(16.1%)	57(83.8%)		
Attitude	Yes	103(39.9%)	155(60.1%)	3.86(1.94-7.68) *	1.92(0.13,0.54) **
	No	11(14.7%)	64(85.9%)		

*Indicate p-value <0.25 in bivariate analysis and **indicate variables having p-value <0.05 in multivariate analysis

DISCUSSION

COVID 19 is an ongoing international public health challenges following influenza, polio, Zika, and Ebola. Although so many trials are commenced since the declaration of the outbreak, still now there is no cure for the disease. Scholars, international and national organizations intensely recommended that adhering to preventive measures is crucial to mitigate the spread and threats of the virus. The overall prevalence of preventive practice of COVID 19 among people attending health facility in Arada sub-city, Addis Ababa was 32.7%. This prevalence was comparable to cross sectional study done in Iranian, which was 4.27% [46]

which was higher than the finding. The prevalence of preventive practice of Covid 19 and associated factors in this study is lower than the finding of cross-sectional study done in northern shoa which was 44.1%[41]. however, it was much lower than the finding of cross-sectional study done in Addis Ababa [43],which was 49%.This might be due to socio-economic ,sample size and geographical difference among study areas. The prevalence of preventive measure of COVID 19 in Another cross-sectional study conducted in Dirashe district, southern Ethiopia was 12.3% .This might be due to different sampling technique and data collection tools[34].In this study showed participant who has formal education were twice protective when compared to those who have no formal education(AOR:1.98;95% CI:1.15,3.45).This might be due increase in ability of understanding there commended measures.

This study indicated individuals with family members of more than five has increased of preventive measure practicing (AOR:1.68;95%CI:,1.04,2.69). this might be due to the thinking of protecting ones self-contribute to protection of the whole family and moreover family members who are aged were at high risk of developing critical illness.

The third associated factor of covid 19 was family monthly income in this study having family income 1000-3000 was increase the chance of practicing preventive measures when compared with the other category (AOR:3.85;95%CI:2.17,6.84). in cross-sectional study conducted in Mexico participants who have monthly income of more than \$800 dollar were practicing preventive measures of covid 19 than middle- and low-income groups [53]. this is due to increase in income gives the ability to buy equipment's recommended by WHO face mask, hand sanitizer such as to protect one's self and they have probability to stay home.

This study indicates participants who are married were practicing preventive measures as compared with those who are single (AOR:2.43;95%CI:1.32,4.42).in cross-sectional another study conducted in southerner Ethiopia gamo zone,those who are unmarried were practicing preventive measures of

covid 19[54]. this might be due to difference in perception of the two individuals and their commitment to practice the preventive measures.

This study revealed that 73.9% of participants involved in this study had a favorable attitude towards COVID 19 preventive measures when compared with study conducted in Oromia region which is 32.2%[55].the possible explanation might be that the respondents who had favorable attitude towards covid 19 preventive measures might trust the science of mitigation measures and comply with the instruction of these guidelines and because of the difference in background characteristics and level understanding.

Our study revealed that 75.6% of participants were knowledgeable about COVID 19. This finding is in agreement with previous studies in Italy (77.4%) [47]. however, it is lower than studies in China (90%) [48], Malaysia (80.5%) [49], Saudi Arabia (81.64%) [50], and Nigeria (99.5%) [51]. This is probably due to the difference in knowledge assessment tool and the cut of point, background characteristics of the participant, awareness creation activities, and channel of information dissemination.so far, in Ethiopia, majority of the information were disseminated through mass media, mobile and social media.

We found this only 32.7% of the study participants adhere with the suggested COVID19 preventive measures. Which is lower than similar study was reported in Egypt and Nigeria 36% [52]. This is probably due to the study participant's difference, means of data collection, measures tool, and cut point used to categorize good poor practice.

7. LIMITATION AND STRENGTH OF THE STUDY

7.1. Strength of the study

As it was done in Arada sub- city it may reflect the actual prevalence of the sub-city.

7.2. Limitation of the study

Study design was cross-sectional so that cause and effect relationship of variables.

The study did not include participants who were utilized private health facility.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

8.1. CONCLUSION

The finding of this study indicates that the prevalence of practicing preventive measure of covid 19 was low compared to previous studies

The result of this study revealed educational status, amount of family members, family income, and marital status were factors determining practice of preventive measures of covid 19 among people attending health centers.

The finding of this study also revealed knowledge level and attitude level were the main factors that determine practice of preventive measures of COVID 19 among people attending health centers.

8.2. RECOMMENDATION

A .For community

Implement preventive measures given from health professional at any place of residence.

Apply preventive measures of covid 19 with available equipment's.

B. for health professionals

Provide information about Covid 19 at any visit.

give continuous advice about the impact of not practicing preventive measures of covid 19.

Encourage those who practice preventive measure of covid 19.

C. for researchers

Further research at the national level.

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55. Adherence to COVID-19 preventive measures and associated factors in Oromia regional state of Ethiopia

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